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Key words: Hero of Uzbekistan, People's Poet of Uzbekistan, Specialized boarding school, "The Youngest Talented Poet of the Year", "Zakovat", "Love Life", International Literature Festival, "Web Design", "Computer graphics", "Creation and processing of audiovisual works", "Visual and digital arts", "Creative club", "Acting skills", "Music magic" clubs.

Abstract: In this article, in order to perpetuate the name of the Hero of Uzbekistan, People's Poet of Uzbekistan Abdulla Oripov, and to select talented students for in-depth study of the native language and literature among the students and further develop their talent, Abdulla in Karshi The state specialized boarding school named after Oripov was established, the activities of the school in educational, spiritual, educational and scientific method fields were analyzed.

In order to perpetuate the name of the Hero of Uzbekistan, the People's Poet of Uzbekistan Abdulla Oripov and to select talented students for in-depth study of the native language and the science of literature among young students and to further develop their talent, the Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan Decision No. 312 of May 24, 2017 [1]. Based on the order[2] and decisions of the Minister of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 176 dated May 25, 2017, the State Specialized Boarding School named after Abdulla Oripov was established in the city of Karshi. Today, 191 students are studying at this educational institution, 50 teachers and employees are working. During the past 3 years of activity[11:73-76], the educational institution has given many first positive results. According to the instructions and tasks set during the visit of the Honorable President Sh. Mirziyoyev on January 29, 2018, a number of measures were taken to increase the creative ability of students and develop educational efficiency [10:396-400] - events have been developed. To date, about 20 students have achieved positive results in Science Olympiads. 12 students participated in contests and contests such as "The Youngest Talented Poet of the Year", "Zakovat", "Love Life", and 52 students participated in various regional competitions. students won. Alisherova Ezoza, a 10th grade student of 2019, participated in the international symposium held in Japan. In the same year, Alisherova was awarded the State Prize named after Ezoza Zulfiya. In the 2019 "Prosperous School" project, the school won in the republic [4:1492-1495]. In order to support the creative abilities of students, more than 10 poems of students were published under the names "Mitti styzn zhilolari", "Yana bahor keldi", "Vatan bakhsti", "Happy children". In October 2019, 2020, a republic-wide scientific-practical conference on the topic "Uzbek language and its current issues", famous linguist and literary scholars[12:26-28], writer and poet, journalist, science[5:135-138]] and a creative meeting with artists and "Skills lessons" were held at a high level. In 2019, the 1st International Literary Festival "OLTIN SOZ" was held and scientists and artists from 8 countries of the world[6:1-6] visited it. Today, 26 skilled specialists of their profession are teaching students at the educational center. 3 of them are excellent people in public education, 1 is a holder of the "Fame" medal, and 1 is a doctor of science. Of course, a newly planted sapling goes through special hardships to grow. In addition to the science clubs at the school of creativity [7:121-123], in order to enable students to acquire modern professions, "Web design", "Computer graphics", "Creation and processing of audiovisual works" ", "Visual and digital art", "Creative club", "Acting skills", "Music magic" clubs are active [3].

Every year, on the eve of Abdulla Oripov's birthday, it has become a tradition to publish the poems of creative students. In 2018, "Followers of Abdullah Oripov", in 2019 "Spring has come again...", in 2021 "Song of Jilgalar", and in 2022 "Glows of Dwarf Stars" was published.

In addition, poems of creative students of this school [8:96-100] were published in the publication "Bouquet from the Garden of Creativity" published by the Agency of Presidential Educational Institutions.

Pupils actively participate [9:128-131] in the science Olympiads held every year and take pride of place.

Tolaganova Maftuna, Hamidov Ramazon, Kholboyev Khushnud, Torayeva Gulsevar, Sobirova Dilnavo, Allanazarova Sevinch, Abdiyeva Sevinch, Choliyev E'zozbek, Badalova Shakhnoza are among them.

In 2021, our student Hamrayeva Sevinch participated in the Uzbek Literature Days International Literature Festival held in Egypt. His poems were published in foreign publications.

In May 2022, Norkulova Marjona visited Italy, and in November-December 2022, Torayeva Gulsevar visited Japan. Of course, such students successfully passed the specified tests and interviews and achieved high results.

In October 2022, the students of the Abdulla Oripov School of Creativity took a proud 2nd place in the Republican tournament organized by the Agency of Presidential Educational Institutions and "Zakovat" (a total of 26 teams participated: Presidential, creative and specialized schools) . Each of them was awarded with a diploma and an expensive gift (laptop).

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